

25 d after maturity. Restorer lines IR9761-19-1R and IR29723-143-3-2-1R can be sown only 30 and 45 d after harvest, respectively. It is safe to market the hybrid seeds 30 d after harvest. ■

Significance of stigma exertion in enhancing outcrossing in male sterile rice lines

C. R. Elsy, M. Rangaswamy, and K. N. Ganesan, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

An investigation undertaken to study the floral characteristics of male sterile lines will lead to better outcrossing and enhanced seed set. Eight cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines were used for the study. Floral characters such as rate of stigma exertion, stigma length and

width, stigmatic area, style length, and natural seed set of these lines were observed during the 1995 wet season.

The natural seed set in these CMS lines ranged between 1.86% in IR68275A and 10.6% in IR58025A, with a mean value of 5.59%. Among the floret characteristics studied, stigma exertion showed a predominant influence on seed set. The mean stigma exertion rate ranged between 6% in IR68275A and 48% in IR58025A. IR58025A, IR68281A, and IR67684A showed a significantly higher percentage of stigma exertion. The significantly higher seed set (10.6%) in IR58025A was attributed to its higher stigma exertion rather than to any other floral characteristics. The genotype with the least stigma exertion (IR68275A) recorded the lowest natural seed set (1.86%). Genotypes with a higher rate

of stigma exertion recorded a higher style length, as observed in IR58025A, IR68281A, and IR67684A. Even though stigma exertion and style length in IR67684A were higher than in other genotypes, seed set was low (4.1%), indicating the linkage factor involved with cytoplasm for male sterility. In IR64707A, multiple stigmas were recorded in 3% of the florets.

Our results indicated that, among floral traits, better stigma exertion should be given maximum importance when developing desirable CMS lines. IR58025A showed maximum seed set (47.68%) and maximum style length (1.22 mm). Although genotype IR67684A showed many favorable floral characteristics for high seed set, it is undesirable because of the interaction of genome and cytoplasm on seed set. ■

Crop and resource management

Fertilizer management

Effect of N levels and time of application on grain yield of hybrid rice

S. P. Singh, B. S. Devi, and S. V. Subbiah, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

During the 1995-96 wet season and dry season, we studied the performance of three hybrids—KHR1, ProAgro 103, and MGR1—using Jaya and Rasi as standard checks. This study included

growth and grain yield performance at four levels of N (0, 60, 120, and 180 kg ha⁻¹). Three schedules of N application were followed: three splits (50:25:25% at basal, tillering and panicle initiation), four splits (25% N at basal, tillering, panicle initiation, and 50% flowering), and five splits (25% N at basal, tillering, and panicle initiation and the remainder applied in two equal splits at 50% flowering and 10 d later). Grain yield differences among the test hybrids and varieties were significant during both

seasons. The maximum grain yields were recorded for ProAgro 103, Vikas, KHR1, and MGR1. Rasi produced 5-14% less grain yield than ProAgro 103. Varieties responded linearly to applied N levels up to 120 kg ha⁻¹. Grain yield differences were not significant among different schedules of N application, indicating that more than three splits of N application are not required for higher grain production by hybrid rice in Vertisol soils. ■

Crop management

Three-drying cultivation of rice: a new technology for rice production in drought-prone areas

Zhou Jie, Zhou Long, Rice Research Institute, Agriculture Bureau, Linyi, Shandong, China

Shandong, China, has a dry spring and rainy summer. In Linyi district, for

example, mean annual rainfall is 872-949 mm, of which 125-150 mm (15%) occur in spring and 560-600 mm (65%) in summer. Because of waterlogging in the wet summer period, grain yields of rainfed crops such as maize, soybean, or sweet potato were often poor in low-lying farming regions. When rice was dry-seeded late in spring after fall

wheat, the medium-duration rice varieties could not ripen because of the shortened growing period. It was difficult to grow rice seedlings because of the lack of water in spring. Therefore, only a fall wheat crop could be grown in the region.

This paper reports research examining the ability to raise rice seedlings,